

D6.1 - GUIDELINES FOR THE FORESIGHT EXERCISE

Authors: Barjolle, D. (lead author), Casabianca F., Maglietti Smith I., Piccin L. (ORIGIN for SUSTAINABILITY), Jaisli I. (UNI-Pisa), Mora O. (INRAE), Schmitt E. (UCO)

November 30, 2022

D6.1: Guidelines for the foresight exercise

Project name	Mountain Valorisation Through Interconnectedness And Green Growth (MOVING)	
Project ID	862739	
H2020 Type of funding scheme	Research and Innovation Action (RIA)	
H2020 Call ID & Topic	H2020-RUR-2019-2 / RUR-01-2018-2019	
Website	www.moving-h2020.eu	
Document Type	Deliverable	
File Name	D6.1. Guidelines for the foresight exercise	
Status	Draft	
Dissemination level	Public	
Date of creation	30 November 2022	
Keywords	Foresight, MOVING H2020 Project, Mountains, Sustainability, Resilience	
Authors	Dominique Barjolle, François Casabianca, Isabella Maglietti Smith, Luca Piccin (Origin for Sustainability), Isabel Jaisli (UNI-Pisa), Olivier Mora (INRAE), Emilia Schmitt (UCO)	
WP Leader	ORIGIN for SUSTAINABILITY	
Project Coordinator	University of Cordoba	

Disclaimer: The content of this document does not reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Responsibility for the information and views expressed therein lies entirely with the author(s).

Table of Content

LIST OF FIGURES.....	4
LIST OF TABLES	4
ACRONYMS.....	5
1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	6
2 INTRODUCTION	7
2.1 KNOWLEDGE BASIS FROM PREVIOUS WORK PACKAGES	10
2.2 INSIGHT INTO THE FORESIGHT EXERCISES AS DESIGNED FOR MOVING	11
2.3 PARTICIPATORY APPROACH IN FORESIGHT.....	12
2.4 PROCESS OF THE MOVING FORESIGHT EXERCISES IN SHORT	12
2.5 FORESIGHT OUTPUTS IN THE NEXT MOVING WORK PACKAGES.....	14
3 GENERAL INSIGHTS ABOUT FORESIGHT.....	14
3.1 DEFINITIONS OF FORESIGHT AND SCENARIO.....	14
3.1.1 <i>What is foresight?</i>	14
3.1.2 <i>What is a scenario?</i>	14
3.2 LINK OF THE FORESIGHT WITH THE MOVING CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK.....	15
3.3 SCOPE OF MOVING FORESIGHT EXERCISES AT LOCAL LEVEL	19
4 MOVING LOCAL FORESIGHT APPROACH.....	21
4.1 TIME SCHEDULE AND DELIVERABLES.....	21
4.1.1 <i>Planning of activities</i>	21
4.1.2 <i>Deliverables</i>	22
4.2 RESEARCH TEAM (RT)	23
4.3 FORESIGHT GROUP (FG).....	23
4.3.1 <i>Role of the FG</i>	23
4.3.2 <i>Composition of the FG</i>	23
4.4 PREPARATORY WORK (RT)	25
4.4.1 <i>Baseline scenario</i>	25
4.4.2 <i>Key-variables</i>	25
4.4.3 <i>Long-term Forces</i>	27
4.4.4 <i>Selection of the two axes for the scenarios</i>	28
4.5 FIRST WORKSHOP	28
4.6 DESCRIPTION OF THE 4 SCENARIOS.....	29
4.7 SECOND WORKSHOP.....	29
4.8 POLICY OPTIONS FOR THE MOST PREFERRED SCENARIO	31
4.9 THIRD WORKSHOP	31
4.10 QUANTITATIVE SURVEY	32
4.11 REPORTING	32
5 FORESIGHT AT CROSS-REGIONAL AND PAN-EUROPEAN SCALES	33
6 APPENDIXES	34
6.1 FRAMEWORK COMPONENTS AND RELATED ANALYTICAL QUESTIONS.....	34

6.2	METHODS TO ELABORATE EXPLORATORY SCENARIOS	35
6.3	TIPS FOR CHOOSING THE MEMBERS OF THE FG	37
6.4	PARTICIPATORY METHODS (EXAMPLES)	39
6.5	APPLICATION OF THE FORESIGHT TO THE SWISS JURA REGION	41
6.5.1	<i>Definition of the scope of the Foresight Exercise for the Swiss Jura</i>	41
6.5.2	<i>Description of the baseline scenario for the Swiss Jura</i>	42
6.5.3	<i>Identification of the key-variables for the Swiss Jura</i>	43
6.5.4	<i>Long-term forces in the MRR</i>	46
6.5.5	<i>Use of visual tools for the Swiss Jura case study</i>	49
7	REFERENCES	54

List of Figures

Figure 1: <i>The 23 selected VCs</i>	9
Figure 2: <i>The MOVING approach (Source: MOVING project, Grant Agreement)</i>	10
Figure 3: <i>The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), adopted on 25 September 2015 as a part of the 2030 Agenda (Source: https://www.un.org)</i>	11
Figure 4 : <i>Mapping of main interactions in the MOVING project: participants -MaPs (Multi-actor Platforms), CoP (Community of Practice), AB (Advisory Board)- related task (T) and estimated timing in months (M) since the project start.</i>	12
Figure 5: <i>Overview of the foresight process</i>	13
Figure 6: <i>The MOVING project framework</i>	17
Figure 7: <i>Apennine Cheese VC, illustrating the linkages with the lamb meat (right) and the lamb wool VCs (left) (source: Moretti et al., 2021)</i>	18
Figure 8: <i>Example of the 4 scenarios based on the 2*2 Matrix approach</i>	29
Figure 9: <i>Categories of scenarios (Reilly and Willenbockel, 2010)</i>	35
Figure 10: <i>Examples of exploratory scenarios matrix applied to food system research.</i>	36
Figure 11: <i>Vulnerability Map for the Permanent Pastures of Swiss Jura MRL</i>	50
Figure 12: <i>Matrix of vulnerability and wooded pastures</i>	51
Figure 13: <i>Increase in average temperatures in Switzerland</i>	52
Figure 14: <i>Projected temperature scenarios</i>	53

List of Tables

Table 1: <i>Planning of activities in WP6</i>	21
Table 2: <i>Description of the composition of the FG at case study level</i>	24
Table 3: <i>Identification of the key-variables in the local FE</i>	26
Table 4: <i>Identification of long-term forces that cause the variations of the key-variables</i>	27
Table 5: <i>Analysis of the long-term forces</i>	28
Table 6: <i>WP6 – Second workshop in each region - Brief summary</i>	30
Table 7: <i>Framework components and related analytical questions</i>	34
Table 8: <i>Example of dimension cards for exploratory scenarios</i>	39
Table 9: <i>Geographical scope of the Swiss Jura foresight exercise (FE)</i>	42
Table 10: <i>Key-variables for the Swiss Jura (this is just an example)</i>	43
Table 11: <i>Example of long-term forces influencing Swiss Jura</i>	47
Table 12: <i>Vulnerability matrix of the Tête-de-Moine PDO VC.</i>	49
Table 13: <i>Percentage of Permanent Pastures area in each Vulnerability Level at Swiss Jura MRL</i>	51

Acronyms

AB	Advisory Board
CAF	Conceptual Analytical Framework
CC	Climate Change
CoP	Community of Practice
DL	Deliverable
EU	European Union
FG	Foresight Group
FE	Foresight Exercise
LTVRA	Long Term Vision for Rural Areas
MaPs	Multi-actor Platforms
MOVING	MOuntain Valorisation through INterconnectedness and Green growth
MRL	Mountain Reference Landscape
MRR	Mountain Reference Region
PDO	Protected Designation of Origin
RT	Research Team
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SES	Socio-ecological Systems
STEEPV	Social, Technological, Economic (macro), Environmental, Political, Values
VC	Value Chain
WP	Work Package

1 Executive summary

The Mountain Valorisation through INterconnectedness and Green growth (MOVING) general approach is focused on ensuring mountain resilience and future sustainable development.

Building on a pan-European Union (EU) conceptual approach, the inventory of 400 value chains (VCs) in Europe, 23 empirically grounded, participatory VC analyses and Foresight Exercises (FE) will identify success factors, future trends and associated drivers at regional, cross-regional cluster and EU levels. These will generate a Policy roadmap and easy-to-use ('Quick Start') Policy design toolkit to foster the sustainable development of European mountain regions, co-constructed with relevant stakeholders.

The present document develops a guiding approach to implement participatory foresight exercises at regional level in the 23 case studies.

The process is as follows:

- Development of a baseline scenario.
- Development of 4 exploratory scenarios based on two selected key long-term forces which are transformed into two axes.

Three workshops will identify the strategies of the actors and the outcomes of the socio-ecological systems for those 4 different explorative scenarios.

In each of the 23 case studies, the exploratory scenarios will be developed considering the importance and uncertainties for two main long-term forces that influence variation of key-variables of their respective socio-ecological systems. The results of the 23 case studies will then be compared with each other, and five foresight exercises will be organised at the wider scale of five clusters grouping the 23 case studies based on a logical classification (outcome of WP5), and a final foresight exercise close WP6, at the EU level. For the latter exercise, the interactive IMPRESSIONS platform (developed in the IMPRESSIONS GA project Nr. 60341627) will be adapted to model the change and interact with stakeholders at European level.

The participatory FEs of the 23 regions, 5 clusters and 1 European will inform the WP7 about policy recommendations. In fact, prospective exercises should envision the desirable future, and identify the policy changes and the other actions needed to achieve it.

2 Introduction

The MOuntain Valorisation through INterconnectedness and Green growth (MOVING) general approach is focused on ensuring mountain resilience and future sustainable development.

Building on a pan-European Union (EU) conceptual approach, the inventory of 400 value chains (VCs) in Europe, 23 empirically grounded, participatory VC analyses and Foresight Exercises (FE) will identify success factors, future trends and associated drivers at regional, cross-regional cluster and EU levels. These will generate a Policy roadmap and easy-to-use ('Quick Start') Policy design toolkit to foster the sustainable development of European mountain regions, co-constructed with relevant stakeholders.

The present document develops a guiding approach to implement a participatory FE at regional level in the 23 Mountain Reference Regions (MRRs¹).

Place of the *foresight exercises* in the MOVING project

The first block of work of MOVING consists in developing the conceptual basis and tools: focused on the definition of the conceptual framework, as a co-learning process (participatory theory building) and visual tools for the subsequent work with the VCs.

The second block is about "Framing and Scoping": identification and characterization of 400 VCs in Europe, to account for the whole diversity of SESs in the mountain areas; selection of 23 representative study cases in the 23 reference regions, to act as pilot cases for the work at local scale.

The third block consists in the assessment of the study cases: participatory analysis of the sustainability and resilience of the 23 study cases at regional scale and the productive systems at EU level; and cross-case comparison and benchmarking in 5 thematic clusters at European scale, to perform a comparative analysis of the resilience and sustainability performance of value chains and to identify success and failure factors against specific vulnerability contexts.

The fourth block is the foresight and the policy recommendations: *foresight exercises* to identify the one (or two) most likely scenarios based on multiple local participative scenarios (trends, assumptions). All the previous results, together with the analysis of the current policy framework at regional and European scales will serve to draft a Policy roadmap and a 'Quick Start' Policy design toolkit conveying the necessary guidelines to deliver the policy instruments needed to foster sustainable and resilient development paths for European mountain regions.

¹ In the context of MOVING, "MRRs" are defined as areas where the landscapes are very similar to the ones of the area where the main VC operates, correspond to NRU3 or similar areas defined with exact geographical delimitations in WP3.

Objectives

The general objective of MOVING-Work-package_6 is to design and carry out FEs based on the visual tools, indicators and models developed in the previous Work Packages (WP) (WP2, WP3, WP4) to enable regional, interregional and European CoP (Community of Practice) (i.e. multi-stakeholder platforms) to co-construct shared strategies and policies that should shape the future towards more sustainable and resilient mountain territories.

The specific objectives are the following:

- Identify the socio-ecological drivers and game changers (social dynamics, technological pathways, development strategies, policy environments) - which are renamed "long-term forces" in this guide to avoid confusion with the "drivers" of WP4 - that will shape the future of 23 mountain VCs by 2050 (cf. Figure 1).
- Produce four Horizon 2050 scenario narratives based on scenario frameworks to assess policy options for the evolution of mountain VCs at European and regional levels.
- Carry out FEs at local, transregional, and pan-European levels.
- Identify trends and dynamics that allow the identification of gaps and needs for policy modernisation to address the identified challenges.

WP6-Team

WP6 is led by ORIGIN, and has support from UNI-Pisa, INRAE and HUTTON.

- Dominique Barjolle, Isabella Maglietti-Smith, Luca Piccin, ORIGIN.
- Michele Moretti, Gianluca Brunori, Isabel Jaisli, UNI-Pisa.
- Olivier Mora, INRAE.
- Kirsty Blackstock, Rachel Creaney, HUTTON.

ORIGIN decided to invite to some key WP6-TEAM meetings for the purpose of coordination among WPs additional members of the consortium:

- Mark Redman, WP7-leader, HIGHCLERE consulting.
- Emilia Schmitt, scientific coordinator, UNI-Cordoba.

- | | | |
|---|--|---|
| 17 Spain
Betic Systems |
| 18 Spain
Sierra Morena |
| 19 Spain
Spanish Pyrenees |
| 20 Switzerland
Swiss Alps |
| 21 Switzerland
Swiss Jura |
| 22 Turkey
Beydaglari |
| 23 UK-Scotland
Highlands and Islands |
| 16 Slovakia
Slovak Carpathian mountains | |

Figure 1: The 23 selected VCs

(Source: MOVING website <https://www.moving-h2020.eu/reference-regions/>)

2.1 Knowledge basis from previous Work Packages

The assessment of sustainability, vulnerability and resilience of mountain VCs is based on the pan-European analysis of the vulnerability of European mountain production systems in relation to climate change and other threats. The results, translated into visual tools, have provided elements for assessment in the 23 reference regions and are used for the local FE.

In the first 24 months, MOVING partners mapped the diversity of VCs existing in all mountain regions of the EU, compiled an inventory of 400 VCs and developed in-depth analyses in case studies in 23 reference regions. The whole approach is reported in Figure 2.

Figure 2: *The MOVING approach* (Source: MOVING project, Grant Agreement)

Ultimately, the project defined the following expected results:

- 1) Identification and characterisation of the main agricultural and forestry systems in the reference regions by advanced spatial analysis combined with existing datasets.
- 2) Assessment of the susceptibility of mountain farming and forestry systems to Climate Change (CC) considering different existing scenarios and produced maps and graphs.
- 3) Identification and classification of the importance of specific drivers and threats in each region.
- 4) Assessment of the exposure and sensitivity of the VC to threats and the local adaptive capacity, and thus the vulnerability and resilience of the VC.
- 5) Definition of the environmental envelope for land use distribution and for establishing thresholds for the profitability of land use systems.

In fact, some results are already available, or are in the process of being made available, while others still need to be clarified based on the data collected in WP2, 3 and 4. The results of Activity 4.5 (point 4 above) are necessary to start the FE in optimal conditions. The last expected result will in our opinion not be achievable in all case studies due to the lack of quantitative data on profitability, but this lack should not be a detriment to the realization of the FE as envisaged in this guide. On the other hand, all the other expected results are necessary, and represent the starting point of the present work. A summary of these results will be

provided to the FG in the form of a baseline scenario from which discussions will be conducted concerning the key variables.

2.2 Insight into the Foresight Exercises as designed for MOVING

These Foresight Exercises (FEs) (WP6) will be:

- creating and exploring plausible scenarios for each of the 23 mountain areas;
- co-constructing shared visions and strategies in FGs in each of the 23 regions, which will be asked about their vision of the mix of public and private goods that is appropriate for the actors in each of the 23 VCs;
- to help local actors to anticipate future problems and develop a common strategy (through scenario building) for better sustainability and resilience of their territory.

The MOVING FEs combine approaches that consider the interactions between the VC and the socio-ecological system (SES) as understood in the MOVING conceptual framework (see Link of the foresight with the MOVING conceptual framework (CAF) 2.2). They will engage stakeholders in developing scenarios for mountain VCs and SESs, a set of SDG-related targets consistent with the vision, and design pathways to achieve the targets.

FEs should enable the identification of:

- technology pathways,
- social dynamics,
- development strategies,
- conducive policy environments,

for resilient and sustainable mountain communities, and therefore support the achievement of The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) as figured out in Figure 3.

MOVING appraisal, assessment and foresight analyses will empower stakeholders and involve them in policymaking, covering major themes such as: the role of local assets, the quality of connections, the business models, the role of women and young people, governance arrangements. (WP1, 4-7).

Figure 3: The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), adopted on 25 September 2015 as a part of the 2030 Agenda (Source: <https://www.un.org>).

2.3 Participatory approach in foresight

In line with MOVING's interactive approach, stakeholders and researchers conduct the local FE in a participatory, co-learning and co-design framework. This FE carried out within the framework of the MOVING project aims to implement a process of accompanying transformation projects by placing the activity and the individuals (their intentions, their projects) at the heart of the participatory process. It consists of imagining future situations by “acting as if” and encouraging each actor to ask themselves how they would act in such a situation.

MOVING's FEs will aim to create exploratory scenario narratives. They aim to open the range of possible futures and the researchers facilitating the exercise position themselves to help actors anticipate future situations with appropriate and robust strategies.

The participatory approach seeks to articulate the diverse and sometimes contradictory expectations of the different stakeholders by building a shared future vision.

In short, the FE will involve stakeholders in the process of building a shared vision. This will help to initiate transformative changes at the community level.

To place the interactions between the case study actors in the broader timeline of stakeholder interactions (face-to-face and distance meetings) during the project, here is the full diagram of all interactions initiated by the MOVING project (Figure 4).

Figure 4 : Mapping of main interactions in the MOVING project: participants -MaPs (Multi-actor Platforms), CoP (Community of Practice), AB (Advisory Board)- related task (T) and estimated timing in months (M) since the project start.

2.4 Process of the MOVING Foresight Exercises in short

The process is as follows (cf. Figure 5):

- Development of a baseline scenario.
- Development of 4 exploratory scenarios based on two selected key long-term forces which are transformed into two axes (e.g., multilevel governance and demography as

for the European foresight exercise for the rural area, called “Long Term Vision for Rural Area (LTVRA)” which was initiated by the European Commission in 2021²).

Three workshops will identify the strategies of actors and the outcomes of the socio-ecological systems to those 4 different explorative scenarios: participants will discuss how the actors will react to expected and unexpected changes and how these reactions will affect the resilience and the sustainability at the scale of the MRR (Mountain Reference Region), or for good reasons, a more specific delimited area (cf. section 3.3 below).

In each of the 23 regions, the exploratory scenarios will be developed considering the 2 most important what we call here “long-term forces” to differentiate them from what was called “drivers” in previous work packages but could be as well designate by “future drivers” in other literature source, leading to most uncertainties and systemic challenges. The results of the 23 regions will then be compared with each other, and FEs will be organised at the wider scale of five clusters grouping the 23 case studies based on a logical classification (outcome of WP5), and a final FE close WP6, at the EU level. For the latter exercise, the interactive IMPRESSIONS platform (developed in the IMPRESSIONS GA project Nr. 60341627) will be adapted to model the change and interact with stakeholders at European level.

Figure 5: Overview of the foresight process

² https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/new-push-european-democracy/long-term-vision-rural-areas_en

The participatory FEs of the 23 regions, 5 clusters and 1 European will inform the WP7 about policy recommendations. In fact, prospective exercises should envision the desirable future, and identify the policy changes and the other actions needed to achieve it.

2.5 Foresight outputs in the next MOVING Work Packages

Building upon appraisal and FEs, MOVING will define a repertoire of strategic options in mountain areas.

This repertoire will assess existing policy incoherence and gaps, will address the policy needs, and will check how existing policies can be mobilised in an integrated policy-mix. This will contribute to the drafting of the necessary policy instruments (WP7).

3 General insights about foresight

3.1 Definitions of foresight and scenario

3.1.1 What is foresight?

Foresight consists in exploring, anticipating, and shaping the future to help building and using collective intelligence in a structured, and systemic way to anticipate developments³. Scenarios are applied at many different scales to resolve specific issues.

Scenarios participatory elaboration and discussion are a way to engage all stakeholders in thinking about many aspects of managing for resilience (Carpenter et al., 2001; Walker et al., 2002), including weighting the short-term cost of possible loss of profits associated with maintaining resilience versus the long-term benefit of not shifting to an undesirable state (Walker and Salt, 2006).

3.1.2 What is a scenario?

Scenarios are descriptions of plausible, possible and/or preferable futures⁴. A scenario study is an approach aimed at bringing strategic and innovative thinking by way of writing scenarios.

During the MOVING project, researchers must describe the implications of each scenario, transforming future developments into strategic policy options that make sense at the level of the MRR, then at the level of clusters (as defined in WP5), and finally at European level.

Scenario definitions are quite diverse. For Kahn (1973), scenarios are “hypothetical sequences of events, built with the intent of attracting attention to causal processes and points of decision” and for Godet (2001), a scenario is “simply a means to represent a future reality in order to shed light on current action in view of possible and desirable futures.”

³ https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/strategic-planning/strategic-foresight_en

⁴ <https://buas.libguides.com/designresearch/scenariostudy>

Scenarios are usually ranged under 3 main categories (Wiebe et al., 2018; Reilly and Willenbockel, 2010):

- **Predictive scenarios** use existing knowledge about the past to derive estimates of future conditions. They are a forecast based on extrapolation of current trends (what is designated as “*long-term forces*” in this document) (Henrich and Zurek, 2007). In MOVING, this projection is designated as the “**baseline scenario**”. The main idea here is extrapolation, and one can only build an extrapolation on a specific trend under *ceteris paribus* (“all else being equal”) conditions.
- **Exploratory scenarios** start from the present and explore the interdependencies of long-term forces in a complex system. They answer the question: “What might happen?”, by exploring the full range of possible futures. They are designed to explore possible futures, including changes in system structure and boundary conditions.
- **Normative scenarios** start from a particular desired vision of the future and work backwards in time to identify pathways to that future. They are designed to support the construction of the vision, developing narratives for the system to achieve specific goals.

3.2 Link of the foresight with the MOVING conceptual framework

The conceptual and analytical framework of MOVING (Moretti et al. 2021) is an unconventional analysis of value addition: it is a broader approach that considers the ways in which configurations of practices undertaken by actors add value to the whole of mountain territorial capital and how these circulate through the stages of VC (Blackstock et al, 2022). It is the incessant feedback loops between agroecosystem, product and people that inform the central issue of the subtle dialectic at the heart of social-ecological systems.

MOVING Conceptual Analytical Framework (CAF) introduces two concepts that are of particular importance for the FE: “assemblage” and “trade-offs between resources and VCs”. **Assemblage** is a way of talking about how social and spatial orders take shape and are reproduced. Assemblage seeks to move beyond the divisions between symbolic/material, structure/agency, and form/process to explain dynamic and contingent socio-spatial formations. The concept has been deployed as a kind of alternative to the idea of 'structure' to explain how socio-material orders take shape. Assemblage is a way of organising heterogeneous entities to function together for a certain period. They are contingent achievements that are always made and remade (*contingency, as opposed to necessity, refers to the possibility of something happening or not happening*).

The **trade-offs** between natural resources and sectoral logics are central elements in the prospective discussion. Indeed, the short-term economic interests of some or all partners in the VC of a particular product or service may prevail in the eyes of these partners, at the expense of natural and sometimes social resources (e.g., human resources may be over- or underpaid). Taking the long-term interests of sustainability, and for example those of biodiversity or air quality, may appear to run counter to short-term economic interests, as some restrictions on resource use may result. It is essential to address controversies and differences

of opinion between stakeholders within territories, positioning the interest of the community as a whole and in the long term, with the sole perspective of achieving acceptable resilience and sustainability and covering the basic needs of humans and non-humans. It is the common framework for all consortium members, in a transversal manner across the WPs.

The conceptual framework is visually represented in the Figure 6 and tends to:

1. Creating a common language in the research community.
2. Inspiring research questions.
3. Helping to gather and classify information.
4. Helping to prioritise issues.
5. Inspiring a narrative.

The conceptual framework is inspired by Ostrom's Socio-ecological Systems (SES) approach and allows to consider the cross-sectional vision of our MOVING project, which is the following: "Mountain VCs are able to create value while improving the sustainability and resilience of mountain social-ecological systems through enabling policy environments capable of supporting local actors in their practices".

The nature of the parts of an assemblage is not defined/operated by the relationships they enter; these elements retain content and action beyond these relationships. Because they are always being (re)assembled, assemblages remain open to transformation ("deterritorialisation"), although the emerging "whole" of the assemblage exerts constraints on the parts that compose it, tending towards the stabilisation ("reterritorialisation") of orders. For example, a product with a Protected Designation of Origin (PDO) is linked to the use of local resources (pastures, acorns to feed animals), but there may be resources coming in from outside. For example, some fodder from abroad (soya, hay) can be used and lead to a certain level of "deterritorialisation".

Figure 6: *The MOVING project framework*

The challenge in the FE is to understand the long-term dynamic inside the SES, and especially how the outcomes are creating all types of different values, being economic, ecosystem related ones, landscapes, wellbeing, livelihoods, and cultural (cf. Figure 6).

In the presentation of the conceptual framework in September 2021, Moretti illustrate two interesting ways of the Apennine Cheese VC, illustrating the linkages with the lamb meat and the lamb wool VCs (cf. Figure 7).

In addition to the two initial VCs of meat and cheese, there was an initiative that did create more values for the territory and the creation of a cooperative for the processing and sale of wool.

Figure 7: Apennine Cheese VC, illustrating the linkages with the lamb meat (right) and the lamb wool VCs (left) (source: Moretti et al., 2021)

In this perspective, by examining how two different combinations⁵ of several VCs impacts the values resulting as outcomes for the socio-economic system in the corresponding MLA, Moretti et al. highlight ten proposals, as follows:

1. Local actors engage in social practices with resource units and with other actors.
2. Practices are aimed at the creation and distribution of value.
3. Social practices develop within the relational space of the actors.
4. The coordination of practices generates VCs.
5. Local actors can either connect to existing VCs or create new VCs through practices.
6. Practices evolve through connections with other practices.
7. Practices are assembled into VCs and business models.
8. Connections between practices can extend to different SES.
9. Through these connections, a VC can influence the sustainability and resilience of SES.
10. Enabling policy environments can support local actors in their practices.

In the foresight, we should consider as well different possible combination of VCs and identify the corresponding expected values of different natures (not only economic but as well cultural, natural, etc.) as resulting of the outcomes of the use of the resources, the type of governance and the practices adopted by the actors. We should envisage all feedback loops corresponding to the analytical grid proposed by Moretti (cf. Appendix 6.1).

Therefore, for the purpose of foresight, we consider the dynamic of the socio-ecological system and the way the SES is building resilience and impacting sustainability at each level being the economy, society, and natural resources. In fact, the transformation of natural resources into commercial products is carried out through techniques which have a mediating function between social systems and agroecosystems.

⁵ For the purposes of this document, and of the FE, we prefer to use the term "combination of several VCs", and not the term "assemblage", which is a difficult concept to handle in the discussions with the field actors during the workshops. Indeed, the term assemblage is useful for the analysis of the discourses and results, but our recommendation is to reserve it for the final report.

3.3 Scope of MOVING foresight exercises at local level

The grands objectives of all FEs (23 regions, 5 clusters and 1 European exercises) are the following:

- To consider the future of each region, based on the dynamics of the VC (identifying and discussing extrinsic long-term forces that influence the key-variables as defined in section 4.4.2).
- To provide information to WP7 on what is needed in terms of policy changes and modernisation, especially regarding the specificities of mountains.
- To provide recommendations at local, regional, cluster and European level, to improve the sustainability and resilience of rural mountain VCs, and their communities.
- To emphasize the specificity of the mountains in the narratives of the scenarios, and in the reporting of the workshops, as well as in the recommendations.

An analysis of vulnerability of the land use system in the WP3 and a workshop to assess vulnerability, sustainability, and resilience at the level of the value chain and its reference landscape at the end of WP 4 (task 4.5) have identified drivers of change, which “*specifies any natural or human-induced factor that directly or indirectly causes a change in a system. A direct driver of change unequivocally influences ecosystem processes and/or sociocultural and economic characteristics and can be identified and measured. An indirect driver of change operates by altering the level or rate of change of other, more direct drivers (...). Such changes can produce negative as well as positive impacts on the analysed systems. An up-to-date literature review reveals a variety of drivers of change causing an impact in the mountain areas (...). In addition, it is expected that even the most recent circumstances, such as inflation, increasing energy prices and pandemics, have a substantial impact on the VCs in mountain areas. Our approach to assess vulnerability is primarily focused on negative impacts and the evaluation of adverse effects on socio-economic systems.*”

As Task 4.5 is an assessment of the current time of research, the drivers of change will be identified as those that have recently had or will have a short-term impact on the VC at the scale of the MRL.

As described in the Description of work: “The FE (*in WP6*) will provide a set of scenarios (4), including: (a) a narrative on how the VCs taken into consideration will affect the resilience and the sustainability of the area (based on the WP3 and WP4 results); (b) a set of economic, social, and ecological indicators (provided by WP2 and used in WP4 for the present-day assessment of vulnerability/sustainability), that will show the distance from the baseline scenario” to most preferred exploratory scenario.

Despite being focused on a relatively large scale, the currently dominant climate scenarios may be useful to apply on a smaller scale as well to assess the potential responses to future climate crisis. However, the enabling nature of such a 'top-down' approach for local communities is debated (Ensor & Berger, 2009; Shaw et al., 2009). WP3 did climate change analysis for all the 23 case studies regions, and the local foresight exercise will build upon them.

Taking this into account, our FE will start with the creation of scenarios at the local level, rooted in the concerns, aspirations, and goals of local communities (Wardekker et al., 2020). Such a 'bottom-up' approach can in turn lead to new ideas about what kind of policies and, moreover, social-ecological interactions, might be relevant to foster resilience strategies for rural communities.

The time horizon influences what elements are included in the foresight. A time frame up to around 25 years ahead enables participants to zoom in on concrete adaptation actions that lead to more resilience (Notten et al, 2003). This time frame is also important for participatory exercises with a knowledge and capacity building goal as to focus on the question of what climate information or any support would be needed, and when.

Time horizon

In terms of foresight, the **time horizon is set at 2050**, a period for which climate forecasts are available in the IPCC reports (the latest was published in August 2022: <https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg1/#SPM>). The FEs have clear medium/long time perspective.

Geographic scope

The geographical scope should be defined according to the most relevant scale for thinking about the future of the Value Chain and its reference landscape, and more broadly, its reference region, as the Value Chain's socio-ecological system (SES) is in the MRR. In the light of these guidelines, future thinking requires a focus on **the local level** to make output relevant for citizens and policymakers (Notter et al, 2003; Crawford, 2019). There are several **entry points for starting the FE: one is the "VC perspective"** for the purpose of differentiating the farming/forestry systems and their incidences on resilience and sustainability. But other entry points must be considered as well because they reflect the local dynamics and challenges in the reference region (for example: other value chains that make use of the land, tourism activities, industry, conservation area, etc.). At the same time, global and national scenarios play a role as context material to assess local visions and their implementation's pathways.

Therefore, the focus should also be broader than the MRL, and lead to the **MRR**. Inputs from experts and policy makers at national level are expected in the work of the FG, to link the VC and its MRL to the MRR but also to the national policy context. In addition, there is some flexibility for RTs to adapt the final choice of the geographical scope of their foresight to a wider or narrower area than the MRL, if there are strong arguments for doing so. In fact, the final decision on geographical scope should help answer the ultimate question guiding the FE in the 23 case studies: "*What are the key factors we would like to know about the future to improve the quality of our decisions?*" and turn around the expected output, which is a strategic policy options repertoire. The focus therefore is on placing the community in the driver's seat: "*what does the community want and how can they make it happen?*"

Motivation of the stakeholders to join the Foresight Group is a key factor for the whole foresight exercise. In that sense, an important point is to have an agenda that fits the needs at local or national level (driving to opening even the participation to other participants for example). It must be clear for everybody, and notably for the members of the foresight group, that this is

not an academic exercise but an attempt to find collective and territorial solutions together and for real. Recalling data and evidence about the changes that are already happening. But we must not discourage the actors. If there are links with other projects in the region, it is beneficial to try to find connections and complementarities between MOVING project and these projects and actors. For example, the implementation of regional climate plans is in line with the MOVING project. If they agree, persons involved in the definition and implementation of such plans should be part of the FE because synergies are likely to happen.

4 MOVING local foresight approach

4.1 Time schedule and deliverables

4.1.1 Planning of activities

The planning of the FE for the 23 case studies is as given in the Table 1.

In September 2023, and together with the WP5, 5 different workshops for the foresight in each of the 5 clusters will be organised.

End of October 2023, European foresight should be organised by AIEDL with members of the European MAPs (Multi-actor platforms).

As a result, the WP6 draft final synthesis report (DL6.3) should be sent to the consortium members, and the reviewers end of November, and the final deliverables should be submitted by the end of December 2023.

Table 1: Planning of activities in WP6

	2022					2023											
	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
<i>Month number in the Grant agreement</i>	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40
Trainings (webinars)		T1	T2	T3	T4	T5	T6		T7					T8			
Setting-up the research team																	
Setting-up the Foresight Group																	
Setting-up the Workplan																	
Preparatory work																	
Workshop 1							1										
Description of the scenarios																	
Workshop 2								2									
Policy options for the most preferred scenario																	
Workshop 3									3								
Drafting the report																	
Conducting the quantitative survey																	
Final report																	

Trainings will be held as follows:

- T1: End of September: historical view, events marking changes, weak signals, introduction to the foresight, role, and composition of the RT

- T2: End of Oct: grand objective of the foresight, role and composition of the FG, differences with the role of the RT, introduction to the baseline scenario
- T3: End of November: email for inviting the FG, preparatory work for the first workshop (baseline scenario, key-variables, long-term forces, selection of the 2 axes to build on the scenarios)
- T4: Mid-December: sharing experiences on the preparatory work, participatory tools and setting-up the agenda for the first workshop
- T5: January: feed-back from first workshop, describing the 4 scenarios
- T6: February: feed-back from second workshop, building up the policy options as back casting for the achievement of the most preferred scenario
- T7: April: Reporting on regional case studies
- T8: September: Small quantitative survey

4.1.2 Deliverables

This is the list of deliverables (D) as expected:

- Adaptation of the DL6.1 in each region: as per Description of Work: “The guidelines (D6.1) will circulate among the partners involved in their implementation, to get feedback to the draft. After delivery of the final guidelines and based on enriched literature review and the conceptual framework from WP2, researchers will carry on a contextualization and an adaptation of the guideline for each case study.”
- DL6.2 – collection of the 23 foresight reports (one per reference region). It will be a report based on the results produced in each region. A template will circulate before the end of the local foresights (January 2023). The final report gathering 23 individual case studies reports is due in month 38 (end of October 2023) and will be confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services). Local reports should highlight the particularities related to the context of mountains.
- DL6.3 - a *synthesis report*, including a *Repertoire of Strategic Options*. Based on the results of the regional, cross-regional, and European exercises, this report will be carried out to provide a comparative overview of all scenarios and a Repertoire of Strategic Options (possible responses of the stakeholders to tackle the challenges). The partner responsible for every case study will draft an internal summary on the results of the local FE, including the strategic local, national, and European policy options, pointing out the needs that are related to the particularities of the mountains. The analysis of the outputs of FEs will allow to build the Repertoire of Strategic Options, including an analysis of the policy needs to shape sustainable and resilient mountain VCs. The main results will be gathered in a policy brief.

4.2 Research team (RT)

The role of the RT is to design, implement and report on the FE in the region.

There is a RT between 1 and more people, who are involved in the FE. In principle, these people are MOVING partners employees. External persons can also be part of this team if they want to participate for their own purposes.

The main responsibility of the team focal point is to communicate with the MOVING WP6 team and to participate in all training sessions. If there are more than 2 persons, we will call them «focal point», «assistant» (if any) and «members».

The responsibility of the assistant is to take over the tasks delegated by the focal point, both operational and representation in case of absence of the responsible person.

The RT meets with the WP6 team at least twice bilaterally during the FE, i.e., at least once before the workshops between November and December 2022, and once after the workshops (between March and August 2023).

The purpose of these planned meetings is to take stock and discuss any outstanding issues. Outside of these meetings, the WP6 leader (Origin for Sustainability) is fully available to answer any questions that are urgent and would block the progress of the work.

4.3 Foresight Group (FG)

4.3.1 Role of the FG

A FG will have to be created to carry out the exercise. The creation of this group is very important, because these people will participate in the three workshops to define the scenarios.

4.3.2 Composition of the FG

Regional stakeholders in the 23 reference regions will be involved in the regional MaPs and will interact online and in face-to-face workshops to contribute to appraisal, assessment, and foresight activities.

As reported in the Table 2, the participants to the FG should include farmers and producers downstream in the VCs, business providers, people involved in different stages of the VC, not only in the region, but also outside, policy makers and representatives of the public authorities at local, regional, and national levels, experts and youngsters and women, from nearby areas interested in the future of rural areas. In concrete terms, the objective here is to bring together a group of **8 to 12 participants** who will take part in the workshops (most of them in all workshops, and a few of them only to some workshops, because being less available but marked as important and influent). One third should be recruited from the MRL, and the rest from the MRR or even beyond (see 3.5.3). The important thing is that these people are involved and that their opinions and skills help build a vision of the territory in **2050**.

This can be the case that a participant belongs to two different categories (like a researcher being as well a part-time farmer). This kind of participant is very welcome in the FG, because he combines different types of knowledge and involvement and can bring a broad perspective in the discussions. It is open and flexible to attach this participant to one category or one other. An important aspect in recruiting the participants is to include a diversity of opinions. There is a need to make clear as a rule for the discussions that all participants should listen and accept the diversity of opinions.

The time and people needed for this will depend on the complexity (one VC – for example Tête-de-Moine PDO (Protected Designation of Origin) – or multiple VCs that are in combination with the main VC – for example Tête-de-Moine PDO + Gruyère PDO + industry milk at MRR scale).

The preparatory work to each workshop should be made available in a format easily accessed by workshop participants for use either before or during the workshop, e.g., an introductory document or a short slide presentation shown during the initial session.

Table 2: Description of the composition of the FG at case study level

FG (different to the MAP)	Choice of the 8-12 participants	Identification of persons that could participate as well, in case of the first persons contacted are not available	Persons that have special knowledge or power, but are not available or no strong interest, but should be interviewed in a bilateral way, or invited to one of the workshops only
1/3 from the MRL (Supply Chain)	Select the 3-4 most involved and interesting people from the MaP, who have already participated in previous workshops.	Identify 2-3 persons who were complementary to the selection done for the 8-12 participants, in case of refusal or late renunciation	Identify a few persons that have strong knowledge, influence, or power for complementary bilateral interviews
1/3 experts	Select qualified and well-known persons and MRR level, or even national level for small countries, with expertise in social, technical, environmental, economic, ethnological, cultural aspects, according to the main drivers of change identified.	Identify 2-3 persons who were complementary to the selection done for the 8-12 participants, in case of refusal or late renunciation	
1/3 policy network	Policy experts at local, national, and regional levels. Consider recruiting people representing different points of view and combining representation/consultation roles at diverse levels (local, national, European, etc.).	Identify 2-3 persons who were complementary to the selection done for the 8-12 participants, in case of refusal or late renunciation	
Other members (open)	Consider recruiting enough women and young participants who are interested in their region and its future, regardless of the viewpoint or interest group to which they belong.	Identify 2-3 persons who were complementary to the selection done for the 8-12 participants, in case of refusal or late renunciation	

4.4 Preparatory work (RT)

4.4.1 Baseline scenario

Baseline scenarios (also known as 'reference' or 'benchmark' or 'non-intervention' scenarios) depict a future state of society and/or environment in which no new environmental policies are implemented apart from those already in place today; a future where activities continue as usual.

It will be used to construct the other scenarios. To develop this baseline scenario, the RTs can start from the historical timeline that was started during the first training (Training#1). The links to the MIRO paintings of the historical figures can be found under this [link](#), and read appendix 5.4 below (section 5.4.2) for reading the example of the baseline scenario for the Swiss Jura.

4.4.2 Key-variables

Based on the work done in the WP3, and WP4, the RT should select the key-variables for the FE. For example, the work done in WP3 provides us with the biophysical drivers of change associated with key resources in each VC studied⁶. For example, extreme events (droughts), higher temperatures and lower precipitation impact quantity and quality of grass in the Tête-de-Moine PDO VC. But there are also other dynamics that have an impact on the evolution of the VC, such as social, economic, and demographic (see the example of Swiss Jura in the annexes). The work done in WP4 is comprehensive enough to provide other information, including beyond the focal VC (assemblages, actors, governance, etc.)⁷. Other useful information can be gathered from the Policy Briefs done for WP2 (<https://data.d4science.net/oDfN>), or from the WP1, like the Task 1.5 on Youth Engagement (<https://data.d4science.net/3J2p>).

In short, partners can extract all useful key-variables from previous work done in the project. These key-variables are elements that are related to resources (all types of resources as figured in Figure 6: *The MOVING project framework*), and pivotal when reflecting on the way of the assemblage around the VC (cf. conceptual framework). They should be limited to 3 to 8, to have a deep understanding of each of them.

Table 3 gives the way to conduct the in-depth analysis of each of the key-variables for each case study.

⁶ Data and information can be extracted from these folder in the VRE : T3.3 Vulnerability analysis - <https://data.d4science.net/Uuqk> ; <https://data.d4science.net/TwVP> ; T3.4 Vulnerability mapping - <https://data.d4science.net/KjiM>.

⁷ <https://data.d4science.net/JHUW>

Table 3: Identification of the key-variables in the local FE

Key- variable	Category	Impacts of changes of the key variable on first level in the VC (production)	Impacts of changes of the key variable on second level in the VC (processing)	Impacts of changes of the key variable on Fourth level in the VC (distribution and marketing)	Other actors of private sector	Consumers' point of view	NGOs	Citizens' point of view	Public authorities	Policy makers
EXAMPLE										
Grass availability and quality	Vulnerability to climate change	- Quantity of milk - Income	- Influence on quality	- N/A	- Input suppliers (fodder, NPK)	- External consumers buy less "distant food" (food miles concerns linked to GHG) ??	- Concerns about climate change (ProNatura, Fridays for Future, etc.)	- Growing criticism against foreign feed imports	- Management strategies (research centres)	- Investment (Barn dryers)

For each variable, it is useful to write a narrative analysis of the impacts, but also to highlight the trade-offs and convergences of interests between stakeholders. For the example in the table, which concerns the Swiss Jura, this is written as follows.

The key variable "availability and quantity of grass in the Swiss Jura" is very sensitive because the vulnerability of this variable to climate change is very high. Therefore, the impacts on the different stakeholders are the following: for farmers, droughts affect the quantity and quality of grass, the first impact is a decrease in the quantity of milk produced per hectare, which has a direct effect on the farmers' income (less milk means less money).

However, the processing level (dairies) is less affected, as the cheesemaker can use milk produced by other farmers, or milk that would have been used for other cheeses or sent for fresh milk or other fresh products to the industry. Cheese makers are indirectly affected by the consequences of the loss of grass quality and thus by the decrease in milk quality, especially in case of a decrease in protein content (especially kappa casein which is the most important factor for cheese processing). This decrease in quality affects the cheese yield and the quality of the cheese, whether it is Tête-de-Moine or Gruyère. But in fact, as there are opportunities to buy or divert milk from other products, the consequences are much less important for cheese makers, ripeners, and traders than for farmers. The industry does not address the current consequences of climate change.

The main way farmers mitigate the effects of reduced grass is to buy fodder and concentrates from outside the region. This is a concern for the long-term reputation of the cheese, particularly with consumers and NGOs, who point to the impact of these imports on greenhouse gas and other emissions, even if they take place outside Switzerland. In addition, as a cheese with a PDO, annual long-term derogations from the code of practice do not please the authorities and certification bodies. Research centres are looking to further optimise grass management strategies, for example by changing grazing rotation techniques or sowing or over-sowing techniques, also by adapting grassland seeds, and the authorities are anticipating the need to provide more water reservoirs for livestock watering, and to switch more farms from industrial milk to cow's milk, to maintain or even increase PDO cheese production from milk produced in the Swiss Jura.

None of the actors is currently considering a long-term strategy to reduce the impact of the milk and cheese production chain on the climate, nor to adapt production to climatic conditions that would really evolve negatively more rapidly than expected.

4.4.3 Long-term Forces

The next step is to analyse more in-depth the key variables, to identify what are the long-term forces behind.

A trend is commonly outside the sphere of direct influence of the VC's actors, but is influencing the VC and more broadly, the MRL, through concrete "mediators" such as the provision of jobs, the rainfall, the financial support, the tax regime, the purchase of products, the membership and material or financial support to a local project, etc. As classical example, the long-term trend behind the change in the rainfall regime is Climate Change.

The **long-term forces** shape future dynamics in both predictable and unpredictable ways. They include some trends in the close-in working environment, like developments related to the stakeholders or local community, as well as exogenous trends -in the broader environment - Social, Technological, Economic, Environmental, Political and Values (STEEPV).

Based on the evidence collected during WP2 to 4, there is a need to identify 3 to 5 long-term forces that influence the main key-variables identified before (Table 4) and rank them according to their uncertainty and importance (Table 5). Uncertain forces are those which are not determined or predictable. As such e.g. demographics are rather predictable, while e.g. public opinion is highly uncertain. For the foresight exercise it is important to choose uncertain long-term forces, so different development in the future is possible (e.g. trade liberalisation versus protectionism).

Table 4: Identification of long-term forces that cause the variations of the key-variables

Key Variable	Visible causes of the variation of the key-variable	Long-term forces that cause the variations	Geographical scale of the causes	Explanation of the link between the long-term forces and the variation of the key-variables
		<i>external/ internal and main cause</i>	<i>local/regional/national/global</i>	
EXAMPLE				
Grass availability and quality	- Higher temperatures - Droughts - Rainfall regime	External Cause: Climate Change	- Global	<p>The rainfall regime is impacted by climate change (more frequent anticyclones). Snow is also less abundant. Following an altitudinal gradient, the phenomenon is less marked. But everywhere the lack of rainfall has a direct impact on grass growth.</p> <p>The average temperature tends to increase. There are more sunny days, especially in summer, which can lead to a slowdown in grass growth (evapotranspiration), in a context of shallow, calcareous (karstic) soils.</p> <p>Droughts are the most relevant drivers. Droughts can lead to significant forage losses.</p> <p>These phenomena seem to be more frequent and prolonged. Hail is also an extreme problematic event as it can negatively affect the quality of the forage.</p>

4.4.4 Selection of the two axes for the scenarios

The two axes chosen to construct the scenario are two of the long-term forces that must correspond to the categories "high impact, high uncertainty". This choice ensures that the parameters of the four spaces defined by their intersection (the scenario matrix, see 3.6) are clearly differentiated.

These axes could be the same as the drivers identified in Task 4.5. in the work package 4. However, there is a high risk that, if chosen with a short-term perspective, the priority is given to drivers that will ask for support policies, including subsidies for investments (such as irrigation or water storage) that mitigate the risks instead of accompanying more deep changes. On the contrary, the idea of the FE is to address long-term and sustainable trends, which may have less short-term priority in the eyes of local stakeholders.

These quadrants may then be developed into scenario narratives, reflecting the influence of previously identified events, trends, and drivers of change, in addition to those already represented on the two axes.

This selection process should care about the relevance and accuracy of each axis. The consistency between the 23 case studies should be as high as possible. Therefore, the WP6-team will discuss it with each local RT in a bilateral way.

Table 5: Analysis of the long-term forces

Long-term forces (reported from Table 5)	Category	Influenced by...	How it influences the key variables	Importance	Uncertainty	Rank
EXAMPLE						
Climate change	Environmental					

4.5 First workshop

The first workshop will

- a) discuss the baseline scenario, as described by the RTRT
- b) discuss and select a short list of key-variables, based on preparatory work done by the RT.

- c) Discuss and decide on the 2 axes (the two most uncertain and important long-term forces that cause variations of many relevant key-variables)

4.6 Description of the 4 scenarios

The RT will then develop a short narrative about 4 different scenarios. This narrative will be discussed and fine-tuned with the FG during the second workshop. **We strongly encourage the RTs to adopt the approach of developing a 2*2 Matrix** ([Rhydderch, 2017](#)). This approach is based on:

- 2 axis which are two drivers (cf. section 3.4.4), which are of high importance and high uncertainty).
- For each axis, there is a need to get well-contrasted expressions of the respective values.

The 2*2 Matrix approach results in the visualisation of 4 explorative scenarios, as very well illustrated in Figure 8:

Figure 8: Example of the 4 scenarios based on the 2*2 Matrix approach (WEF, 2017)

A short narrative (as for the baseline scenario) should explain each category in a few lines, that are a basis for the explanations given as introduction to the second workshop.

4.7 Second Workshop

In the second workshop (cf. Table 6), the FG should:

- a) give a feed-back on, and refine, the narratives for the scenarios proposed by the RT give a feed-back on the 4 scenarios proposed by the RT, adding missing elements or commenting on the key-variables and their value for each scenario. This discussion should as well allow to find the level of agreement among the participants, and the reasons behind possible disagreement if any. The objective is not to reach a consensus but to identify the main reasons behind the possible divergences of opinions.
- b) choose and consolidate the description of the most preferred scenario (based on the refining of the choice of key variables and their valuation according to a converging “desired future”, which should take as well into account their probability of occurrence)

All stakeholders’ opinions, including ‘dissent’ positions, will be documented, and illustrated.

Table 6: WP6 – Second workshop in each region - Brief summary

Exploratory Scenario Development Workshop	
What to do	Invite the FG as defined in section 4.3.2. If the actors are not available or are too far away from each other, it is possible to organise the discussion online and with appropriate tools (e.g. Miro boards).
Why we do it	The Workshop will highlight the prior issues and substantial concerns among our stakeholders regarding the interactions between VCs and SESs in each region. To address these concerns, we decided to use the exploratory 'scenario axes' methodology to develop narrative scenarios of change focussed on the management of territorial resources to 2050. The aim of this workshop is therefore to identify what our stakeholders consider to be the key long-term issues regarding resilient strategies and sustainable management processes at present and in the future.
What to achieve	We want to know from our stakeholders what they consider to be the most important long-term forces affecting the territorial resources of their regions. For this, we will need to foster momentum and support for the scenario process among our stakeholder group.
Possible problems	To avoid problems and uncertainties we have planned training sessions prior to the scheduled workshop. We will have to be careful of the process of driver elicitation and scenario axes selection, to avoid conflicts. We also invite the regional teams to anticipate, to schedule the workshop considering the time constraints of the stakeholders.
Tips	Be creative! There are several different ways to accompany the unfolding of the scenarios. Just try to make the process simple and intuitive. Examples of workshop facilitation methods are provided; for example, the use of stickers and/or post-it (the latter case can be replaced by Miro) for the identification of bullet points. We believe that practice of the workshop process is vital, and that making sure workshop participants are familiar and comfortable with the process is an essential ingredient in successful scenario facilitation. We recommend having an assistant to take notes, allowing the facilitators to focus on the comments and workshop process.

4.8 Policy options for the most preferred scenario

The second workshop should ask the FG members about their preferences for the scenarios and get them to select one as the most preferred. Arguments and differences of opinion are important to make as explicit as possible, as they reflect important aspects of each scenario from **several** important perspectives, which hide constraints and limitations that should be accompanied by targeted policy measures to realise their full potential in the next phase of defining the accompanying policy options for realising the preferred scenario.

The last part of the second workshop consists of a brainstorming on the accompanying policy measures for the realisation of the preferred scenario.

Starting from the objections to the choice of this scenario by some participants, but also by asking all participants about the constraints that prevent the realisation of this scenario under the current political conditions, ideas for new framework conditions are to be collected without censorship or limitation, in the form of a new and very open idea collection.

The RT should then pool all this harvesting of policy and other types of adaptations and changes that could support the realisation of the most preferred scenario. For the policy, there is need to address all the relevant policies (spatial planning, infrastructure investment, agricultural, veterinary, rural, regional, environmental, food, health, etc.) with the different types of measures (normative, subsidy incentives, compulsory or voluntary measures, support for training or entrepreneurship, support for research, one-off or permanent support, support for infrastructure or training institutions, etc.) and the levels of decision-making (local, regional, national and European). For the other types of changes (business, NGOs, projects, events, digital platforms, etc.), that would be possible to initiate without public support, there is nice to get them identified as well, to discuss them with the stakeholders during the third workshop.

This preparatory work should remain quite simple and will be discussed, prioritized, and fine-tuned during the third workshop.

4.9 Third workshop

In the third workshop, the preferred scenario is refined, and its related strategic changes and policy options are discussed based on the analysis and review done by the RT. The FG discussions should give a clear direction, and therefore priority, to the changes that need to be made for the scenario to be realised. The recommended approach is to identify intermediate steps (about 2 to 5 milestones) by examining backwards from the vision of the ideal scenario to the current situation.

For each milestone, the existing or future policy measures, as well need for actions for other stakeholders like businesses, NGOs, civil society, local inhabitants, etc. are identified. The RT members can make new proposals based on a literature search in relation to similar situations in other contexts, for example in other countries or mountain regions, in the European Union or outside. Participants can also propose ideas to introduce novelties, or suggest significant improvements in instruments or procedures, when significant bottlenecks are clearly identified.

The workshop concludes with a weighting phase to identify critical points in the intermediate steps and milestones of the implementation pathways, and priority needs in the improvement

of existing policies, and in the changes towards the introduction of new policy measures (i.e. policy options). This weighting can be done through a limited number of points to each of the participants. Each participant allocates then the points he/she gets to certain points on the long list of needs that have been identified. Then, the points that have more total points are listed as “priority points”, and they will be given higher weight in the conclusion.

A discussion of the policy needs to enable sustainable and resilient mountain areas will be assessed by the participants and then after, compiled in the Repertoire of strategic options which will feed the content of WP7.

4.10 Quantitative survey

A quantification will be carried out, through a questionnaire turning the assessment of the 2 most preferred scenarios and their related most preferred policy options (as weighted in section 4.9 just above) into an evaluation of impacts, through Likert scale.

This questionnaire will be elaborated in English and then, translated in all other needed languages by the operating consortium partners, administered face-to-face to a group of stakeholders (representatives of ages, of genders, of education and of sectors of activities) in the 23 reference regions (to get 30 to 100 answers for each, depending on the case study). reference region, depending on the case study, namely the size of the population of the MRR). Face-to-face may be organized with a questionnaire administrated in the streets. Questionnaire should not take long (max 5-10') and should harvest the opinion of the population regarding scenario and policy options preferred by the FG regarding aspects that may concern the population in general.

This will allow gathering their preferences and get accurate data on quantitative evaluation of scenarios and policy options.

4.11 Reporting

The final report for each region will follow a template to be provided in January 2023.

The report will be short and will essentially include the elements prepared by the research team:

- The personalised work plan for carrying out the foresight exercise for the case study, mentioning whether elements of previous foresight exercises exist and are available. These existing elements can profoundly modify the approach to carrying out the MOVING exercise, as it is a question of capitalising on what already exists in order to continue to mobilise the actors instead of redoing an extraction of information which would be felt as an unnecessary constraint by the actors on the spot.
- composition of the foresight group
- the compilation, analysis and presentation elements prepared by the RT.
- the minutes of the foresight workshops and bilateral discussions with experts and decision-makers who were unable to attend the workshops. Anonymisation of the participants should

ensure confidentially, except for statements that should be attributed to persons or functions, for which informed consent will be mandatory.

- Analysis tables on key variables, identification of long-term forces, ranking of trends for the identification of axes, 2*2 matrix diagram and scenario narratives.
- Synthesis on the need for adaptation and public policy changes, as well as needs identified for all types of initiatives from the other stakeholders, to support the realisation of the preferred scenario.
- a one-page executive summary.

5 Foresight at Cross-regional and Pan-European scales

The previous part was devoted to the work of each local RT in the 23 regions. Based on the 23 reports and main results, the research teams should consolidate the results at country level when there is more than one case study in the same country.

Next, cross-case workshops will be a follow-up of cross-case comparison and benchmarking carried out in WP5, and the organization of cross-case workshops will be done in collaboration with WP5 leaders. They will work with the scenario narratives developed for the regional exercises but will enlarge the analysis to include cross-regional interactions. This will lead to benchmark the resilience and sustainability performance of the different VCs with a focus on the trade-offs between the provision of public and private goods in the mountain areas, in the existing or potential combinations of VCs and the environmental and social threats identified. Emphasis will be put on the innovative approaches to mountain in economies identified and on how VCs can secure the long-term provision of public goods.

Finally, the scenarios and policy options will be discussed at pan-European level to draw conclusion to European policy actions that could support the emergence and happening of the best local and regional scenarios. The pan-European workshop will be carried out in collaboration with AEIDL and with the support of UK Centre for Ecology & Hydrology (UKCEH), an independent, not-for-profit research institute, which will implement the modelling at European level with a web platform from the FP7-project IMPRESSIONS. This should provide visualisation of changes of many aspects (like the land use, the demography, etc.) based on the assumptions elaborated for each scenario. Those changes will be done at European level, instead of local, and with a more aggregation level but more broad view of the effect of the changes on many variables.

A final foresight workshop will be organised with selected EU MaP members and invited experts. This will be an opportunity for participants to discuss and clearly state the need for adaptation and policy change towards a preferred scenario for the EU-wide foresight group.

6 Appendixes

6.1 Framework components and related analytical questions

Table 7: Framework components and related analytical questions

Framework components	Analytical questions
VC	How are practices assembled into the analysed VC? How have practices been adapted to the SES's resource unit/resource system? What is the importance of the relevant practices in the VC? Which types of connections are identified for the actors within the observed VCs? Which is the degree of flexibility and diversification of the connections established by primary producers in the assembled VC? Are the actors connected with other VCs? How did the actors change the practices when joined other connected VCs? Who are your main customers and suppliers in the VC? What are the most important functions/activities/flows in the VC?
Resource Units	What are the resource units the practices and the VC rely upon?
Resource Systems	What are the resource systems the practices and the VC rely upon (exploit, valorise)? Which of these resource systems are internal and which external to the SES? How are they geographically distributed? Are these resource systems under- or over-exploited? How can we measure their sustainability? Are exploited resource systems private, public or collectively owned? What is the geographical distribution of resource systems involved in value creation?
Actors	Who are the relevant actors involved in the VCs? Which are the actors performing the practices? Are they individual or collective? How do actors justify the way they do their practices?
Governance	What formal and informal governance systems shape or influence the practices at the local level? Which technological pathway provides the background against which practices have developed? What are the power relations within the assembled VC, with special regard to small players (e.g., small farmers)? Did the VC's governance system has changed? If yes, how? Does the local governance system support local actors in the realization of practices? And in the creation of new practices?
Outcomes	What are the outcomes of the practices? What values (economic, social, cultural, ecological, symbolic) are generated? From which practice most of the value comes from? How does your VC contribute to resilience and sustainability of the local SES? Which characteristics and which functions of the VC can reduce the identified vulnerabilities for the SES and enhance its resilience?
Socio-economic and political setting	Which norms and formal and informal rules shape or influence the practices at the regional, national, and global level?
Related Ecosystems	What are the resource units or actors external to the local SES? Do identified assemblages connect the case-study SES with other SESs? How many different SES are telecoupled through the VC? Where are they located, also in relation to the SES under study? How are the values (or dis-values) distributed among the telecoupled SESs?

Source: Moretti et al, 2021.

6.2 Methods to elaborate exploratory scenarios

2*2 Matrix ([Rhydderch, 2017](#))

This approach is based on:

- 2 axis which are two long-term forces, which are of high importance and high uncertainty.
- For each axis, there is a need to get well-contrasted expressions of the respective values.

The 2*2 results in 4 explorative scenarios.

Morphological Approach ([Godet, 2000](#); [Johanson, 2018](#))

This approach is based on:

- Various drivers
- Various expressions of each driver

The result is any number of combinations, and therefore, of scenarios.

Source: *Exploring the future of land use and food security: A new set of global scenarios*, ([Mora et al. 2020](#))

Figure 9: Categories of scenarios ([Reilly and Willenbockel, 2010](#))

Regarding food systems, the scientific literature provides examples of exploratory scenarios that we present in the following figures for inspiration.

Figure 10: Examples of exploratory scenarios matrix applied to food system research.

6.3 Tips for choosing the members of the FG

TIP 1 - Understand the interests and influence of stakeholders in the process

You will need to spend some time conducting a stakeholder analysis. Normally, by this stage of the MOVING project, each RT should have established good relationships with local stakeholders or at least have knowledge of key partners. If this is not the case, we recommend face-to-face meetings with key potential participants - calling or visiting individuals to understand what motivates them and convince them to become an active member of the process. Remember, this is a two-way process, and stakeholders will want to know what influences you.

TIP 2 - Plan how you will engage stakeholders from the beginning

From the beginning of the process, a clear picture of who needs to be involved and why, as well as their interests, will facilitate decisions about the processes in which they should be involved.

For example, social and climate experts can be recruited to identify the drivers of climate change, while decision-makers can be identified for mainstreaming adaptation measures and taking responsibility for these measures.

An appropriate mix of stakeholders will help to facilitate the process throughout the different stages.

TIP 3 - Keep stakeholders interested and informed. Beware of stakeholder fatigue.

For most of the regional case studies, stakeholder fatigue and institutional change with its attendant staff turnover can be limiting factors.

You can use flyers, brochures, audiovisual materials, websites or blogs, social networks, mailing lists as communication tools. Also, reporting back after each workshop is a positive action. The important thing is to keep the motivation in the group so that every participant comes to each of the three workshops. You can organise the first one or two workshops remotely, using tools like Zoom or Teams. At least one workshop must be held physically.

TIP 4 - Ensure good facilitation and knowledge of your methodology

In each RT there must be people who can plan the timing of activities, resolve or prevent conflicts between stakeholders with differing views, or know the right time to provide information to participants (see 3.3.1.). It will also be essential that specific techniques are used (such the identification of drivers or the backcasting) and are well understood by the facilitator, and should be well prepared and practiced before the meetings take place. To help you, specific training sessions are planned by the WP6 leader.

TIP 5 - Don't overlook the logistics of workshops

When planning a workshop, the following should be considered:

- appropriate invitations;
- the venue;
- food and drink (if any);
- seating arrangements, acoustics and temperature of the room;
- send the agenda and an informative summary to delegates before the event.

Also make sure that your event does not coincide with events such as football matches or council meetings, for example. This can make all the difference in getting stakeholders involved, excited and comfortable, and ready to give their best.

6.4 Participatory methods (examples)

Participatory methods are essential to facilitate focus group deliberation. The role of the facilitator is to open up spaces in time where participants feel safe to express themselves with authentic views and opinions on sensitive topics.

Each RT can choose from this toolbox and use the method it prefers to support its stakeholders. However, if the RT is hesitant, we particularly recommend the method described in example 2.

EXAMPLE 1 - Poker design cards

What?

Poker design cards can be used by participants to explore futures based on local citizen narratives collected in early interviews, surveys or focus groups.

When?

In participatory exercises with exploratory scenarios.

How?

Following Wardekker et al. (2020), who experimented with poker design cards in the Gulf of Morbihan, France, it is possible to use cards that contain relevant elements of which citizens thought could impact the local context (see the table below). They can be divided in three categories:

- climatic changes and hazards;
- infrastructure and territory;
- resources and actors.

Table 8: Example of dimension cards for exploratory scenarios

Poker design categories	Categories of narratives			
	Geo-social	Historical	Seasonal	Climatic effects
Climatic changes and hazards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Submersion • Flooding • Erosion 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drying soils • Sea level rise • Ocean acidification 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Warmer summer and spring periods • Colder winters 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Storms • Heat waves • Droughts
Infrastructure and territory	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First nautical mile • Subsidence • Beaches 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Oyster farms • Coastal pathway • Salt mines 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Second homes • Ports • Water treatment systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Historical sites • Urban areas • Routes
Resources and actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Island owner • Intra-gulf nautical transport network 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Oyster farmers and farmers • Direct selling • Tourists 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Office of Tourism • Retired population • Seasonal workers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Measuring instruments • Scientific community

(source: Wardekker et al, 2020)

Participants are asked to randomly pick one card of each category and use these to describe possible future situations. The cards can easily be created from images taken from the web and printed at home (or in a print shop).

Citizens can also narrate about more desirable futures with regards to their local context. Visions of a better future can also be used as content of poker design cards as an inspiration source for participants when developing their own visions.

EXAMPLE 2 - Post-its

What?

Post-its turn vague thoughts and ideas into concrete actions or options. This is a classic method, relatively easy to implement.

When?

In participatory visioning exercises.

How?

During visioning exercises post-its can structure desires, assets and values into a more coherent vision.

By associating a concept with a visible artefact that can be used by everybody, the use of post-its facilitates collective reflection.

1. During the workshop, ask people to write down key ideas on post-its (1 idea/post-it, written in a readable way).
2. Collect the post-its on a suitable surface (board, flipchart, table, etc.) to see and manipulate the information.
3. Choose a method to capitalise or discuss the ideas. You can sort them by affinity (group together post-its that refer to similar or close ideas), and/or give points to the different proposals (for example with coloured stickers, or with your hands...).

Beyond these two examples, there are a lot of possible practical foresight methods and tools for organising civil society participation in the process of building climate-resilient and sustainable futures. At [this link](#), you can download a toolbox with participatory foresight methods, tools and examples from climate and food governance⁸.

⁸ van den Ende M, Wardekker A, Mees H, Hegger D, Vervoort J. (2021). *Towards a climate-resilient future together: A toolbox with participatory foresight methods, tools and examples from climate and food governance*. Utrecht, the Netherlands: Utrecht University Press.

6.5 APPLICATION OF THE FORESIGHT TO THE SWISS JURA REGION

6.5.1 Definition of the scope of the Foresight Exercise for the Swiss Jura

While the time scope is defined in a standardised way (2050), the geographical scope can be more problematic to set. In the case of Tête de Moine PDO, we can start from the area of the designation of origin, which is clearly identified in the product specifications (see WP3 maps). In our case, this area corresponds to the MRL.

However, as we have seen in the work done for WP4, the reality is complex. Indeed, on the one hand, different production systems coexist in this production area (e.g. even at the farm level several production activities can be combined, dairy and/or beef cows, pigs, fodder production, horses, etc.); on the other hand, production practices lead producers and VC actors to work with actors from outside this area, for example by introducing fodder from elsewhere (hay from France or Italy). Using CAF terms, we can say that production, distribution and sales, and consumption practices can result in different kinds of assemblages and telecouplings. The Tête-de-Moine PDO VC is combined with other VCs:

- Gruyère PDO
- Industry milk
- Cow breeding
- Horse breeding
- Forestry
- Touristic activities

The production of all these VCs can be organic or not, and this has an impact on the resilience and sustainability performance of the region. Diversification of the farms influence mostly the resilience level.

For example, a milk producer may supply milk for the Tête de Moine PDO, but also for the Gruyère PDO, which covers several cantons in Switzerland. Similarly, at the distribution and marketing level, certain actors (cheese dairies, distributors) have extensive commercial relationships, even at the national (retailers) and international (Swiss Cheese Marketing) levels. In addition, the authorities intervene at the local (municipalities), regional (cantons), national (agricultural policy) and even international (trade and legal agreements on the protection of origin) levels.

It is therefore essential to consider systematically, by posing the pros and cons, all these aspects discussed in the previous phases of MOVING, to define both the participants of the FG and the geographical scope.

Table 9: Geographical scope of the Swiss Jura foresight exercise (FE)

Geographical scope	Arguments for this perspective	Arguments against this perspective
MRL (=Tête-de-Moine area)	<p>Increasing sales trends for cheese.</p> <p>Existence of public projects promoting the transition from "industrial milk" to "cheese milk".</p> <p>Positive global dynamics, with retention of added value in the territory.</p> <p>Persistence of an important link with SES (wooden pastures).</p> <p>High proportion of local grass in the cows' ration (min. 70%, according to the specifications).</p>	<p>Commercial logics leading to external sourcing of fodder or internationalisation of sales, with a tendency for value capture by the downstream actors.</p> <p>Modernisation of agriculture supported by past policies (at cantonal and/or national level), often leading to concentration and separation between trees and pastures.</p>
MRR (all Swiss Jura)	<p>Timeline 2050 // CC perspective // market scale // the technical opportunities: all those elements are the same across this geographical area</p> <p>Main policy influence (Agr) is the same across the country, which do not belong to EU</p> <p>The natural conditions are very similar all over the Jura Mountain</p>	<p>Complexity of the implementation of the agricultural policy through 3 different cantons (Jura, Neuchâtel, Vaud), where the financial capacities (therefore some of the subsidies for the investments) are very different.</p>

Finally, in the Jura case, the MRR is the geographical scope for the foresight, but all workshops will be organised in the Jura Canton, and a few stakeholders from the Tête-de-Moine PDO will be invited, as a follow-up from the first part of the analysis of the situation.

6.5.2 Description of the baseline scenario for the Swiss Jura

The baseline scenario should answer the following question: *what if we take advantages of all possibilities we have identified in the current state of market and policies?*

It is about to identify a business-as-usual trend. In our case, actors could be satisfied with the current market trend, and live on their achievements, without any concern for the "red lights" associated with climate change. This also refers to the consideration of public policies. As noted in the youth engagement workshop, these policies tend to protect farmers much more than in the rest of Europe, for example through high levels of public support, but this can also be a brake on innovation and, ultimately, on adaptive capacity.

The work carried out in the previous phases of MOVING is comprehensive enough for the RT to answer this question.

BASELINE SCENARIO

In 2050 the **ageing agricultural population** and **policies still anchored in the paradigm of modernisation** will lead to a **concentration of structures**. In the Swiss Jura, there are fewer and fewer farms that are producing PDO milk, dropping from the current 238 to 150.

Young people are less and less attracted to dairy cattle farming, because the income is not the same as before and the workload is high: they do not want to spend the whole year in the barn. Thus, retirements are not replaced by new breeders. The farmers who remain buy the land of their neighbours, and the farms are therefore getting bigger and bigger, which requires intensive management, based on mechanisation and major investments that are difficult to pay back in the short term.

This dynamic has an impact on the **landscapes** of wooded pastures, with an increased tendency to dichotomy with forest on one side and forage areas on the other.

The **grassland resource is weakened** due to **climate change**: droughts, higher average temperatures, lower precipitation reduce the amount of grass available in summer. Farmers' incomes are negatively affected.

The **export market is stagnating** or even declining.

A negative spiral is set in motion, leading to a **crisis in the dairy farming sector**.

6.5.3 Identification of the key-variables for the Swiss Jura

RT did identify a list of key variables that have been identified in WP3, and during interviews and workshops with the local stakeholders.

This part of the work is mainly based on the *interpretation* by the RT of the results produced in the previous WPs. It is an overview of the variables, both biophysical and socio-economic and cultural, that impact the trajectory of the SES and VC.

Table 10: Key-variables for the Swiss Jura (this is just an example)

Key- variable	Category	Impacts of changes of the key variable on first level in the VC (production)	Impacts of changes of the key variable on second level in the VC (processing)	Impacts of changes of the key variable on Fourth level in the VC (distribution and marketing)	Other actors of private sector	Consumers' point of view	NGOs	Citizens' point of view	Public authorities	Policy makers
Grass availability and quality	Vulnerability to climate change	- Quantity of milk - Income	- Influence on quality	- N/A	- Input suppliers (fodder, NPK)	- External consumers buy less "distant food" (food miles concerns linked to GHG) ??	- Concerns about climate change (ProNatura, Fridays for Future, etc.)	- Growing criticism against foreign feed imports	- Management strategies (research centres)	- Investment (Barn dryers)

	<p>TRADE-OFFs & CONVERGENCES : The key variable "availability and quantity of grass in the Swiss Jura" is very sensitive because the vulnerability of this variable to climate change is very high. Therefore, the impacts on the different stakeholders are the following: for farmers, droughts affect the quantity and quality of grass, the first impact is a decrease in the quantity of milk produced per hectare, which has a direct effect on the farmers' income (less milk means less money). However, the processing level (dairies) is less affected, as the cheesemaker can use milk produced by other farmers, or milk that would have been used for other cheeses or sent for fresh milk or other fresh products to the industry. Cheese makers are indirectly affected by the consequences of the loss of grass quality and thus by the decrease in milk quality, especially in case of a decrease in protein content (especially kappa casein which is the most important factor for cheese processing). This decrease in quality affects the cheese yield and the quality of the cheese, whether it is Tête-de-Moine or Gruyère. But in fact, as there are opportunities to buy or divert milk from other products, the consequences are much less important for cheese makers, ripeners, and traders than for farmers. The industry does not address the current consequences of climate change.</p> <p>The main way farmers mitigate the effects of reduced grass is to buy fodder and concentrates from outside the region. This is a concern for the long-term reputation of the cheese, particularly with consumers and NGOs, who point to the impact of these imports on greenhouse gas and other emissions, even if they take place outside Switzerland. In addition, as a cheese with a PDO, annual long-term derogations from the code of practice do not please the authorities and certification bodies. Research centres are looking to further optimise grass management strategies, for example by changing grazing rotation techniques or sowing or over-sowing techniques, also by adapting grassland seeds, and the authorities are anticipating the need to provide more water reservoirs for livestock watering, and to switch more farms from industrial milk to cow's milk, to maintain or even increase PDO cheese production from milk produced in the Swiss Jura.</p> <p>None of the actors is currently considering a long-term strategy to reduce the impact of the milk and cheese production chain on the climate, nor to adapt production to climatic conditions that would really evolve negatively more rapidly than expected.</p>									
<p>Water</p>	<p>Natural resources</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Access - Quantity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Access - Quantity 	<p>- N/A</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Access - Quantity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Quantity/Quality for private consumption 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Quality for fauna - Biodiversity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Quality - Quantity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - strategies (research centres) <p>Management (research)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Investment - Quantity - Quality
<p>Wooden Pasture</p>	<p>Natural resources</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Tree density - Shade on grass (buffer effect) 	<p>- N/A</p>	<p>- N/A</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Access to wooden pastures for leisure & tourism - Use of trees for forestry activities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Heritage & amenities - Symbolic values - Leisure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Biodiversity - Landscape's preservation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Access to traditional landscapes - Sense of place 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - strategies (Natural parks, research centres) <p>Management (Natural)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integrated management plans?
	<p>TRADE-OFFs & CONVERGENCES : There is a convergence between the scientific actors and the population on the importance of wooded pastures. Ecologists and biologists have shown the important role that trees play in preserving grass (buffer effect) during droughts. These landscapes also have a role in preserving biodiversity. They are also recognised by the population and by studies in the humanities and social sciences. They give a sense of place and have a powerful identity, as shown by the number of tourists and activities with a high symbolic value (preparation of the "torrée" meal in the woods, horse riding, trekking and Nordic skiing, etc.). Nevertheless, the preservation of wooded pastures is uncertain, due to policies that are essentially rooted in modernisation, and which only partially recognise the status of this particular socio-ecological system.</p>									

	<i>"Integrated management plans" are tools that aim to bring these different stakeholders together, but they are still recent and complex to implement.</i>									
Milk Robot usage	Technical progress	- Access	- Influence on quality	- Influence on quality	- Mechanical engineering industry	- Image	- Image - Influence on Biodiversity in milk and cheese	- Image - Social and Ethical concerns	- Encourage the adoption of the robot to limit the workload and maintain rural activities	- Need for new regulations
	<p>TRADE-OFFS & CONVERGENCES : <i>The milking robot is a subject that crystallises important debates in the Swiss agricultural sector.</i></p> <p><i>The case of Gruyère PDO, the largest Swiss cheese designation of origin, serves as an example for the smaller Tête de Moine PDO. In fact, the Gruyère interprofessional association prohibits the use of robots.</i></p> <p><i>The Tête de Moine interprofession takes the same defensive line, following what is happening in the neighbouring Gruyère PDO.</i></p> <p><i>However, the workshop with young farmers in the Jura region showed us that they are in favour of adopting the milking robot. According to them, it allows them to enhance the value of their farming activity by making it more attractive and less arduous. They also consider that this activity has a positive image in the eyes of consumers, because cows are more free and less stressed with this system based on artificial intelligence.</i></p> <p><i>However, these claims need to be proven by further investigation.</i></p> <p><i>Other producers and consumers do not see things in the same way, and think that this is a technological headlong rush, a move away from tradition. So the debate remains open on this uncertain theme.</i></p>									
Grass rate in cows ration	PDO specifications	- Origin of fodder (local or not) - Quantity of grass in the ration	- N/A	- N/A	- Organic stores?	- Concerns about animal wealth	- Image - Support for more grass in the ratio (ecological concerns)	- Image - Social and Ethical concern	- Producers organisations - Natural Parks	- Net zero policies?
	<p>TRADE-OFFS & CONVERGENCES : <i>The amount of grass in the cows' ration is a sensitive issue. Indeed, the PDO specifications prescribe that at least 70% of the ration must be composed of fodder from the farm.</i></p> <p><i>This quantity is important, especially as silage is prohibited. However, in dry years, producers who limit themselves to this percentage have difficulty because they are forced to import more than 30% of their feed from outside the area.</i></p> <p><i>Defenders of a more ecological agriculture point to the example of organic farming, whose specifications require 95% grass in the ration. This trend is validated by scientific research, which proves that grass-based livestock systems have a better ecological balance and a strong reduction of GHG emissions.</i></p> <p><i>The public authorities seem to be following this trend, but they also have to deal with the internal resistance within the farming sector, and with the various types of learning and investment that this change of production rule implies.</i></p>									
Export	Market	- Increasing marketing costs can no longer be afforded by producers	- 60 % of sells go to export	- Profit (National and international chains/stores) - Stagnation or loss of international sells?	- N/A	- Premium price for organic or PDOs	- Concerns about GHGs	- ?	- Support for promotion (Swiss cheese marketing)	- Carbon taxes/labels?
	<p>TRADE-OFFS & CONVERGENCES : <i>Tête de Moine PDO is a success story. It is a source of pride for the people of the region. Nevertheless, the share of exports has become the majority of the cheese's sales. More than 60% of sales are abroad, especially in Germany and France. This trend stimulates production in the appellation area, which is favourable, but the added value is often captured by the downstream actors in charge of exports (distributors, certain cheese dairies, retailers).</i></p> <p><i>Because the price paid to farmers remains the same, whether they sell directly or in the region's cheese dairies, or whether their cheeses are sold at two or three times their price in luxury shops or restaurants.</i></p> <p><i>Moreover, this trade risks being weakened in the future, if the locavore trend strengthens everywhere (notably in Europe), and if the decarbonisation of the economy continues, for example with measures such as the carbon tax.</i></p> <p><i>In short, economic growth in in trade-off with a search for quality, including in its environmental dimension.</i></p>									

Price paid by consumer	Business viability	- Producers struggle to maintain added value on the territory	-	- Make margin for profit - Increasing value added		- Premium price for organic or PDOs ?		Less meat and search of more healthy diets and lifestyles	- Territorial management/marketing	- Innovation policies
<p>TRADE-OFFs & CONVERGENCES : Products with a PDO label benefit from a premium price, which to date has made it possible to retain the added value in the territory and to ensure that producers are properly remunerated.</p> <p>The PDO system has proved to be resilient, as during crises such as those linked to the end of quotas or to variations in the CHF/EURO exchange rate (10 years ago). During these crises, the prices of PDO products have proved to be more stable, even if the quantities sold have been less important. This has to be compared with industrial milk producers, whose prices have fallen and where only the largest farms have resisted. However, with the importance of exports, an increasing part of the value is captured by the downstream, reducing the effect of the PDO on the income and viability of the farms.</p> <p>Moreover, the development of organic farming leads to questions regarding the PDO's labeling and strategy: can the two labels converge, particularly with a high proportion of grass in the ration, or should they remain separate and reach two different, well-targeted customers?</p>										
Financial support for non-business activities	Provision of public good	- Landscape management practices - Biodiversity management - Agroecological infrastructures	- Use of local and/or renewable energies in dairies	- N/A	- Renewable energy and forestry sectors (Local actors of the building and construction industries)	- Link between product and place (wooden pastures) - Preservation of cultural and natural heritage	- Biodiversity and landscape preservation	- Access to traditional landscapes - Sense of place - Preservation of cultural and natural heritage	- Green direct payments	- Need for new regulations (Green and integrated policies)
<p>TRADE-OFFs & CONVERGENCES : Actually, at the interprofessional level (which is the main collective actor of the Tête-de-Moine VC), the natural environment isn't well considered. Policies are just starting to consider the role of wooded pastures. They should give a special status to woodland pastures, firstly to recognise their importance, and secondly to accentuate research for a better adaptation to climate change, such as diversifying the tree species. To limit the dependence on public support and exports, policies should also promote diversification, innovation and short supply chains. Indeed, the diversification of agricultural activities directly on farms, such as through the development of agritourism or the promotion of other agricultural products, could limit these dependencies and thus increase resilience.</p>										

6.5.4 Long-term forces in the MRR

STEP 1 - Key variables overview

The question we need to answer is: "What are the long-term forces that will affect the key variables identified in the previous step?"

The first step is to discuss and sort through the key variables identified by the research team and discussed with the foresight group during the workshop. This can be done using the STEEPV methodology (based on Rydderch, 2017).

The mnemonic STEEPV stands for: Social, Technological, Economic, Environmental, Political and Values. It is a broad categorization of external, macro domains affecting all organisations. When developing strategy, STEEPV reminds participants to consider current or potential activities, trends, and developments in all these domains — not just in the immediate environment. Participants reflect on how these activities, trends and developments might impact their own organisation. The STEEPV technique encourages actors, be they individuals or organisations, to look more deeply, and think about their operating environment with a longer-term perspective.

However, other categories can be identified, for example we have used the category "climate change", which is more explicit and broader than "environment", as climate change highlights the impact of human activities on climate and ecosystems.

Table 11: Example of long-term forces influencing Swiss Jura

Key Variable	Visible causes of the variation of the key-variable	Long-term forces that cause the variations	Geographical scale of the causes	Explanation of the link between the long-term forces and the variation of the key-variables
		<i>external/ internal</i>	<i>local/regional/ national/global</i>	
Grass availability and quality	- Higher temperatures - Droughts - Rainfall regime	External (Climate Change - Environment)	- Global	The rainfall regime is impacted by climate change (more frequent anticyclones). Snow is also less abundant. Following an altitudinal gradient, the phenomenon is less marked. But everywhere the lack of rainfall has a direct impact on grass growth. The average temperature tends to increase. There are more sunny days, especially in summer, which can lead to a slowdown in grass growth (evapotranspiration), in a context of shallow, calcareous (karstic) soils. Droughts are the most relevant drivers. Droughts can lead to significant forage losses. These phenomena seem to be more frequent and prolonged. Hail is also an extreme problematic event as it can negatively affect the quality of the forage.
Water	- Rainfall regime	External (Climate change - Environment)	- Regional	Karst soils accentuate the problems associated with reduced rainfall. Prolonged droughts and higher average temperatures lead authorities to restrict the use of water, which thus becomes a precious commodity. Water can be scarce in the pastures, especially in the mountain pastures.
Milk Robot	- Techno - PDO code of practice	Internal (Technological)	- Local	To cope with the workload (milking cows 365 days a year), some farmers and professional organizations have proposed to introduce milking robots. These have the advantage of automating milking, for which human presence is no longer necessary. Nevertheless, several criticisms are raised. For example, a part of the agricultural world puts forward the fact that this automation can have negative impacts on the quality of the milk. Others consider that this technical innovation can negatively affect the image that consumers have of livestock farming...
Wooden pastures	- Agricultural practices	Internal (Political)	- Local	Wooden pastures are a heritage emblem of the Franches Montagnes region, the birthplace of Tête-de-Moine PDO cheese. They are associated by the inhabitants of the region with peace and quiet, with spiritual values and with a strong attachment to the place. Their importance is increasingly emphasized by scientific studies, which highlight the buffer effect of trees on grass growth. Yet, woodlands have little recognition

				in public policy. Trees in pastures are not replaced because they are considered of little value to the wood industry. Also, mechanized management of grasslands is easier if trees are absent. We are therefore witnessing a dichotomic trend, with meadows on one side and grouped trees on the other, which could lead to the disappearance of this landscape of great patrimonial and ecological importance.
Financial support for non-business activities	- Agricultural policy	Internal/External (Economy/Political)	- Local/Regional	Actually, at the interprofessional level (which is the main collective actor of the Tête-de-Moine VC), the environment isn't well considered. Policies are just starting to consider the role of wooded pastures. They should give a special status to woodland pastures, firstly to recognise their importance, and secondly to accentuate research for a better adaptation to climate change, such as diversifying the tree species. To limit the dependence on public support and exports, policies should also promote diversification, innovation and short supply chains. Indeed, the diversification of agricultural activities directly on farm, such as through the development of agritourism or the promotion of other agricultural products, could limit these dependencies and thus increase resilience.

STEP 2 – Ranking

Once the 3 to 5 long-term forces influencing the main key variables are identified, the foresight group proceeds to rank the trends, according to two criteria: importance and uncertainty. This step is crucial, as it leads to the choice of the two axes, according to which the scenario matrix will be built by the research team in the following step.

Going through the trends one by one, workshop participants discuss how important each one is to the focal issue already identified in the previous step. They then add their degree of uncertainty.

The trends identified must be presented to the foresight group. The members of the foresight group discuss and then rank the two criteria for each trend in a participatory way. This can be done with coloured stickers or post-its. For example: green = very uncertain/important; yellow = medium; red = less uncertain/important (Other ways are possible, for example with a scale from 1 to 10). Once each FG member has spoken, the overall number of votes is counted. The trend with the highest number of green stickers (or the higher scale) for both the uncertainty and importance criteria will be selected.

If more than two are identified, the 2x2 method requires either combining (grouping) two or more drivers into a more broadly defined long-term force or considering different pairs of trends as potential axes for the 2x2 matrix.

6.5.5 Use of visual tools for the Swiss Jura case study

In this section we present a series of visual tools that should be used to guide the foresight group during the workshops. Some of the visual tools have been developed in previous phases of MOVING, while others come from secondary sources.

- VISUAL TOOLS FROM THE MOVING PROJECT

In WP3 we made a vulnerability matrix and a vulnerability map. In the case of the Swiss Jura, we selected 2 main drivers for the vulnerability analysis in the WP3:

- Driver 1: Altitude
- Driver 2: Landscape Mosaic Structure (tree cover density).

Table 12: Vulnerability matrix of the Tête-de-Moine PDO VC.

Vulnerability Matrix (Assessment based on the analysis of the information collected on Task 3.3)			LUS Differentiating Criteria		
			Elevation		
			< 600m	600 - 950 m	≥ 950 m
LUS Differentiating Criteria	Landscape Mosaic Structure	Grazed woodland (≥ 70%)	2	2	1
		Very wooded pasture (20%-70%)	3	2	2
		Lightly wooded pasture (1 % - 20%)	4	3	2
		Non wooded pasture (≤ 1%)	5	4	3

At elevations up to 600 m with a tree cover density up to 1% the vulnerability of permanent pastures to the vulnerability drivers identified above was considered very high (level 5). On the contrary, at elevations above 950 m with a tree cover density above 70% it was considered very low (level 1).

The geographical area defined by the Tête-de-Moine PDO cheese specification is essentially made up of pastures (from 415 m to 1606 m). These areas are divided into communal wooded pastures; permanent communal grazed meadows; permanent private grazed pastures; temporary meadows mown for fodder.

Which are the drivers and how do they affect the Land Use System?

- Altitude

Altitude reduces the effects of all elements that affect the quality and quantity of grass. These elements are precipitation regime, higher temperatures, droughts (extreme events). Indeed, it is known that temperatures decrease in correlation with altitude (adiabatic gradient). Thus, in summer, low altitude pastures are more vulnerable to the identified change factors, while higher pastures are less vulnerable. Moreover, in these higher areas, these changing conditions suggest a favourable trend as they favour grass growth in spring and autumn. The summer pasture areas ("estivages") are interesting in dry years. Their higher altitude relieves the pressure on lowland pastures which are subject to heat waves and a halt in grass production in summer. For example, in the summer of 2003 and spring of 2011, droughts caused a 40% drop in the annual yield of pastures in the Jura

plain. Finally, droughts make it increasingly difficult to establish and maintain the botanical balance of temporary grasslands, especially on lowlands (< 600 m).

- Mosaic structure of the landscape

The fine mosaic structure of woodland pastures significantly reduces the effect of drought on fodder production. Maintaining a semi-open landscape with trees would allow farmers to mitigate the negative effects of climate change on fodder production and stabilise yields. Assuming an increase in the frequency of dry years, wooded pastures have the potential to reduce the economic risk associated with large fluctuations in the amount of available grass, which would force farmers to buy additional fodder.

Description of the classes:

- 2.4- non-wooded pasture: intensive to semi-intensive pasture, almost without trees and generally without shrubs. Tree cover rate: $\leq 1\%$
- 2.3- Lightly wooded pasture, with fine texture: intensive to extensive wooded pasture. Mostly isolated trees. Tree cover rate: between 1 and 20%
- 2.2- Very wooded, coarse-textured pasture: semi-intensive to extensive wooded pasture, with trees grouped in groves separated by grouped in groves separated by a network of "chambers" (grazed meadows, thin lawns). Tree cover rate: between 20 and 70%
- 2.1- Grazed woodland: generally, very extensive, almost devoid of grazed meadows and rough grassland. Tree cover rate: $\geq 70\%$

Figure 11: Vulnerability Map for the Permanent Pastures of Swiss Jura MRL

Most permanent pasture area was classified with a vulnerability level of 3 (medium) 57.55%. Vulnerability levels 4 (high) and 2 (low) occupy 21.60% and 13.11% of the permanent pastures area, respectively.

Table 13: Percentage of Permanent Pastures area in each Vulnerability Level at Swiss Jura MRL

Vulnerability level	LUS area (%)
1. Very low	6.31
2. Low	13.11
3. Medium	57.55
4. High	21.60
5. Very high	1.43

For example, in the case of the Tête-de-Moine PDO, we found in the scientific literature (Barbezat et Boquet, 2008) different images of wooded pastures. These images correspond to different afforestation rates of the pastures. We used them to create this visual representation of wooded pastures.

Figure 12: Matrix of vulnerability and wooded pastures

The four images are separated by two axes based on the vulnerability matrix: one axis for altitude (low - high), a second axis related to the afforestation rate. From an ecological point of view the best scenario is top right: heavily wooded pasture above 950 metres. Conversely, non-wooded pastures below 600 metres are the most vulnerable. From a strictly ecological point of view, the hypothesis of the total disappearance of trees should be avoided, as it increases the risk for the grassland resource. But the farmers may need quite large areas of meadows. Multiple trade-offs must be made between farmers and forestry services, landowners, and other stakeholders. So, the intermediate scenarios can be evaluated positively as good compromises between multiple human and non-human actors and logics.

In short, this visual representation reinforces the results of the vulnerability analysis by adding the landscape dimension, to which the inhabitants of the region are very attached (Droz et al, 2013).

These tools are important to generate discussions and to reflect on the dynamics underway. Still in the case of the Swiss Jura, we can also complete these visual tools from WP3 with the information from WP4.

Other factors, both economic, social and cultural, have an impact on the evolution of these landscapes. The loss of interest in communal pastures, the preference for wood from intensively managed forests, the increasing use of mechanisation in agriculture, or the “silos rural policies” do not favour an optimal management of these landscapes.

On the contrary, a dichotomization is observed, with mechanically managed meadows devoid of trees, and on the other side forests inaccessible to livestock and therefore without grazing.

However, the buffering effect of trees against climate change is scientifically recognized (Barbezat et Boquet, 2008; Buttler et al, 2012), as well as the landscape value for different audiences (tourists, inhabitants, etc.) (Droz et al, 2013).

- Other visual tools

To highlight the importance and effectiveness of climate change, other visual tools can be mobilised from secondary sources. Each research team can use whatever visual tools or data it considers appropriate for this purpose. The only condition is that the information is always scientifically sourced and substantiated, as in these two examples.

Figure 13: Increase in average temperatures in Switzerland

(Source: NCCS (Hrsg.) 2018: CH2018 - Klimaszenarien für die Schweiz. National Centre for Climate Services, Zürich)

Figure 14: *Projected temperature scenarios*

Figure 14 illustrates the predicted variation of near-surface temperatures between 2021 and 2050, compared with the reference period 1971-2000. The image clearly shows how mountain areas will be more affected by rising temperatures than other European areas.

7 References

Andreescu, et al, (2013). Understanding normative foresight outcomes: Scenario development and the 'veil of ignorance' effect. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, Scenario Method: Current developments in theory and practice, 80 (4): 711–22

Banos V. & Mora O. (2017) Du débat public, la délicate mise en œuvre d'une stratégie d'action: les enseignements de la prospective "Massif des Landes de Gascogne. l'horizon 2050". *Sciences Eaux & Territoires*, 1, numéro 22, pp. 18-23.

Barbezat, V.; Boquet, J.-F., (2008). *Gestion intégrée des paysages sylvopastoraux de l'Arc jurassien - Manuel*. La Chaux-de-Fonds, Besançon.

Blackstock, K., et al, (2022). D4.3: Report on participatory VC analysis, MOVING deliverable.

Buttler et al, (2012), *Recherche Agronomique Suisse* 3 (7–8): 346–353, 2012

Callon, M. (2021). *Markets in the Making: Rethinking Competition, Goods, and Innovation*. Princeton University Press.

Canniford, R., & Bajde, D. (Eds.). (2015). *Assembling Consumption: Researching actors, networks and markets* (1st ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315743608>

Crawford, M. M. (2019). A comprehensive scenario intervention typology. *Technological Forecasting & Social Change*, 149, 119748. doi:10.1016/j.techfore.2019.119748

Droz, Y., Miéville-Ott, V., & Forney, J. (2013). Les crêtes du Jura suisse à l'épreuve des éoliennes : un patrimoine menacé ?. In Juhé-Beaulaton, D., Cormier-Salem, M., de Robert, P., & Roussel, B. (Eds.), *Effervescence patrimoniale au Sud : Entre nature et société*. IRD Éditions. doi :10.4000/books.irdeditions.8824

Ensor, J., Berger, R., (2009). *Understanding climate change adaptation: lessons from community-based approaches*. Warwickshire, UK: Practical Action Publishing.

Mora, O. (2018) *Land use and food security in 2050: a narrow road*. Versailles, Quae.

Moretti, M., Brunori, G., Grando, S., Felici, F., Scotti, I., Ievoli, C., Belliggiano, A., (2021), D2.1 Conceptual and analytical framework draft, MOVING deliverable.

Godet (2000), *The Art of Scenarios and Strategic Planning: Tools and Pitfalls*, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0040162599001201>

Hebinck, A., et al (2018) *Imagining transformative futures: participatory foresight for food systems change*. *Ecology and Society* 23(2):16.

http://www.impressions-project.eu/show/IAP2_14855

Le Mou.I C., de Lattre-Gasquet M., Mora O. (eds) (2018) *Land Use and Food Security in 2050: A Narrow Road*. Ed. Quae. Free book (Agrimonde-Terra): <https://www.quaeopen.com/produit/107/9782759228805/land-use-and-food-security-in-2050-a-narrow-road>

Mora O., Banos V., Regolini M., Carnus J.-M. (2014) Using scenarios for forest adaptation to climate change: a foresight study of the Landes de Gascogne Forest 2050. *Annals of Forest Science*, 71 (3), pp. 313-324.

Mora O. & Banos V. (2014) La forêt des Landes de Gascogne : vecteur de liens? *VertigO - la revue électronique en sciences de l'environnement*, vol. 14, n°1, 23 p.

Mora O., Riba G., Hubert B. (2010) Vers de nouvelles ruralités? *Territoires 2040*, n°2, pp. 93-100.

Notten, P. W. F. van, Rotmans, J., Asselt, M. B. A. van, & Rothman, D. S. (2003). An updated scenario typology. *Futures*, 35(5), 425-443. Retrieved from <https://www.narcis.nl/publication/RecordID/oai:cris.maastrichtuniversity.nl:publications%2F97e7126b-ec87-43e7-8557-10bd2ee42201>

Shaw, A., Sheppard, S., Burch, S., Flanders, D., Wiek, A., Carmichael, J., Robinson, J., Cohen, S., (2009). Making local futures tangible — Synthesizing, downscaling, and visualizing climate change scenarios for participatory capacity building, *Global Environmental Change*, Vol. 19, 4, 447-463.

Wardekker, A., Ende, M. van den, Marschütz, B., Pijnappels, M., Hofland, S., et al. (2020). Incremental scenario case studies. CoCliServ report D2.2. CoCliServ, Guyancourt

Webpages:

<http://institut.inra.fr/en/Objectives/Informing-public-policy/Foresight/All-thenews/New-Ruralities-in-France>

<https://prodinra.inra.fr/ft?id={0BC36B6DA28B-4B2E-BDC5-C1496D70B808}&original=true>

<https://inra-dam-front-resourcescdn.wediagroup.com/ressources/afile/447196-35604-resource-prospective-agrumes-corseresume.Pdf>

<http://institut.inra.fr/en/Objectives/Informing-public-policy/Foresight/All-thenews/Agrimonde-Terra-foresight-study>